

Revisiting vertical models to simulate the lineshape of electronic spectra adopting Cartesian and internal coordinates

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Abstract

Vertical models for the simulation of spectroscopic lineshapes expand the potential energy surface (PES) of the final state around the equilibrium geometry of the initial state. These models provide, in principle, a better approximation of the region of the band maximum. At variance, adiabatic models expand each PES around its own minimum. In the harmonic approximation, when the minimum energy structures of the two electronic states are connected by large structural displacements, adiabatic models can breakdown and are outperformed by vertical models. However, the practical application of vertical models faces with the issues related to the necessity to perform a frequency analysis at a non-stationary point. In this contribution we revisit vertical models in harmonic approximation adopting both Cartesian (\mathbf{x}) and valence internal curvilinear coordinates (\mathbf{s}). We show that when \mathbf{x} coordinates are used, the vibrational analysis at non-stationary points leads to a deficient description of low-frequency modes, for which spurious imaginary frequencies may even appear. This issue is solved when \mathbf{s} coordinates are adopted. It is however necessary to account for the second derivative of \mathbf{s} with respect to \mathbf{x} which here we compute analytically. We compare the performance of the vertical model in the \mathbf{s} -frame with respect to adiabatic models and previously proposed vertical models in \mathbf{x} - or \mathbf{Q}_1 -frame, where \mathbf{Q}_1 are the normal coordinates of the initial state computed as combination of Cartesian coordinates. We show that for rigid molecules the vertical approach in the \mathbf{s} -frame provides a description of the final state very close to the adiabatic picture. For sizeable displacements it is a solid alternative to adiabatic models, and it is not affected by the issues of vertical models in \mathbf{x} - and \mathbf{Q}_1 -frames, which mainly arise when temperature effects are included. In principle the \mathbf{G} matrix depends on \mathbf{s} , and this creates non-orthogonality problems of the Duschinsky matrix connecting the normal modes of initial and final states in adiabatic approaches. We highlight that such a dependence of \mathbf{G} on \mathbf{s} is also an issue in vertical models, due to the necessity to approximate the kinetic term in the Hamiltonian when setting up the so called GF problem. When large structural differences exist between the initial and the final state minima, the changes in the \mathbf{G} matrix can become too large to be disregarded.

1 Introduction

Electronic spectroscopies provide detailed information about the electronic structure of molecular systems, allowing a deeper understanding of their optical and electronic properties and, consequently, their use spreads over many fields of research, including material science or photobiology. Computational simulations able to directly predict spectral lineshapes represent a powerful tool to extract all the information underlying the experimental spectra. Indeed, within the Born-Oppenheimer approximation, the simulation at room temperature of the vibrational lineshape associated with electronic spectral bands is now at hand for large semi-rigid molecules thanks to the advances on both time independent (TI)¹⁻⁵ and time dependent (TD)⁶⁻¹⁴ techniques (see refs. 5,6,15-18 for recent reviews). This is possible not only in gas phase but also in solution. In fact, methods based on implicit solvent models, like Polarizable Continuum Model (PCM)¹⁹ allow to account for mean solvent effects on the potential energy surface (PES) of the solute (and hence on the vibrational progressions).^{20,21} Additionally, different strategies, based on either implicit^{13,22} or explicit^{23,24} solvent models, have been recently proposed to estimate the solvent inhomogeneous broadening, leading to a completely non-phenomenological simulation of the spectral shapes.

The limitation to semi-rigid systems stems from the necessity, for large molecules, to rely on the harmonic approximation to describe the PESs of the electronic states involved in the electronic transition. The model PESs are quadratic curves constructed from a truncated Taylor series at a relevant point of the real PES. For the initial state such a point corresponds to the equilibrium geometry, while for the final PES two different formulations are commonly used,^{25,26} namely adiabatic and vertical, in which the harmonic PES is constructed at its own minimum or at Franck-Condon (FC) point, i.e. the minimum of the initial state, respectively. The differences in the adiabatic and vertical approaches reflect the anharmonicity of the final-state PES. Here we focus on models that take into account the differences of the Hessians of the initial and final states. In the recent past we proposed to name them Adiabatic Hessian (AH) and Vertical Hessian (VH) models, respectively.^{5,27} Both methods finally provide a linear transformation between the normal modes computed for the initial and final PESs, the Duschinsky relation,²⁸

$$\mathbf{Q}_1 = \mathbf{J}\mathbf{Q}_2 + \mathbf{K} \tag{1}$$

where \mathbf{Q}_1 and \mathbf{Q}_2 are the normal modes in the initial and final PESs, \mathbf{J} is the Duschinsky matrix and \mathbf{K} the normal mode shift vector but AH and VH values for \mathbf{J} and \mathbf{K} , as well as for the final-state frequencies are in general different.

The harmonic approximation is well suited for rigid systems while usually, when the structural differences between the initial and final state minima become significant, remarkable anharmonicities occur. In these cases and for adiabatic models, it has been shown that the accuracy of the harmonic approximation also

depends on the coordinate frame used to describe the normal modes. Concretely, the use of Cartesian coordinates (\mathbf{x}), which have an intrinsic rectilinear nature, quickly leads to strong mode-mode couplings, appearing as Duschinsky mixings and anharmonic effects for modes undergoing curvilinear displacements, such as those occurring along torsions.²⁹ On the contrary, the use of curvilinear valence internal coordinates \mathbf{s} (bonds, angles and dihedrals), which are better adapted to molecular motions, helps to extend the applicability of the harmonic approximation even to cases where sizeable curvilinear displacements occur.²⁹⁻³⁵ Moreover \mathbf{s} coordinates are also the most natural basis for more refined treatments aimed to include anharmonic effects along specific modes.^{31,36,37}

As a matter of fact, in the same problematic situations where the adoption of curvilinear coordinates is recommended, i.e. when sizeable curvilinear displacements occur, a moment analysis of the spectrum indicates that vertical models should be preferred to adiabatic models, at least when the target is the reproduction of the region of the spectral maximum.^{25,38,39} In fact, by construction, the vertical model PES better describes the FC region of the real PES. It is therefore clear the interest in using internal coordinates also for VH models.

In recent years a number of different VH approaches have been presented in literature which differ for the coordinate frame adopted to express the final state Hessian: the initial-state normal coordinates (\mathbf{Q}_1 -space),²⁷ Cartesian coordinates (\mathbf{x} -space),³² linearised internal coordinates (\mathbf{S} -space),³² and, very recently, curvilinear internal coordinates (\mathbf{s} -space)³⁵ but an in-depth analysis of their relative performance in practical cases is missing. Therefore we decided in this contribution to compare them extensively both from the mathematical point of view and checking, in practice, the difference of their predictions. In fact, in spite of the aforementioned advantages, VH models normally face an important issue since the FC point is not, in general, a stationary point of the final state PES. In such circumstances, the vibrational analysis is more complicated since, as we will highlight later, a full separation of the Hessian along vibrational and rotational coordinates cannot be achieved in Cartesian coordinates. In this contribution we clarify that VH models in \mathbf{x} -, \mathbf{S} -, and \mathbf{Q}_1 -frames (when the normal modes are computed as linear combination of Cartesian coordinates) are all equivalent (since now on we refer to them speaking of the \mathbf{x} -frame) and all suffer from this possible issue. The latter can be instead solved using curvilinear internal coordinates \mathbf{s} . Unfortunately this complicates the calculations since, in order to properly compute the Hessian matrix, it is necessary to consider the derivative of the transformation (the so called Wilson \mathbf{B} matrix) from \mathbf{x} to \mathbf{s} coordinates. Therefore, with very few exceptions,³⁵ such derivative has been disregarded in the past assuming that it introduces negligible additional terms.³²

In this work we decided to investigate the consequence of this approximation in detail. To that end we adopt valence internal coordinates and compute the derivative of the \mathbf{B} matrix with respect to Cartesian coordinates analytically. With this tool we study, on a series of different dyes, the impact of such term on the

vibrational frequencies and normal modes and on the simulation of the spectral shapes, an analysis that, to the best of our knowledge, has not been yet reported in literature. In this way we document that \mathbf{x} -frame can exhibit problems that are solved within the \mathbf{s} -frame approach which, therefore, should be the method of choice. In fact we show that with \mathbf{x} -frame even flashy artifacts can appear, like the prediction of spurious imaginary frequencies, that do not exist if the \mathbf{s} -frame is adopted.

The occurrence of imaginary frequencies has plagued so far the applicability of the VH model as it puts in crisis the harmonic approach itself. Therefore it has been often overcome in the recent past with simple solutions that cannot avoid some degree of arbitrariness, like the neglecting of the problematic modes³² or the assignment to them of “reasonable” real frequencies.²⁷ Beside the necessity to conceptually clarify the nature of the problem, these pragmatic solutions introduce a bias in the computation that is not easy to control. Our results indicate that, solving these problems, the adoption of the \mathbf{s} -frame makes the vertical model more straightforwardly applicable. It should be recalled, in this respect, that true imaginary frequencies can of course occur in the final-state Hessian. For instance, Hazra and Noijeen⁴⁰ proposed a wise vertical method to extend the applicability of the vertical model, even in the challenging cases when double-well profiles are met (provided that anharmonicity involves one or few coordinates), using the same machinery developed for harmonic systems. A pre-analysis of the final-state Hessian in terms of curvilinear internal coordinates can individuate those imaginary frequencies that are just spurious, allowing to adopt the elaborated protocol devised in ref. 40 only to the modes that really require it.

More in general, we will document that the problems of the \mathbf{x} -frame extend also to real frequency modes but they are however mainly confined to those exhibiting low frequencies and that, therefore, their impact on the simulation of the spectral shapes is especially relevant when thermal effects are considered.

The focus of this contribution is not on the comparison with experiment which clearly depends also on other factors like the choice of the electronic method, and within Density Functional Theory (DFT), of the functional. On the contrary, we aim at investigating the different predictions of the spectral shapes that arise from different possible vertical models. Therefore, we found expedient to select a number of molecules with different degree of flexibility, for which AH model has already shown to work reasonably well in comparison with experiments, and for all the vibronic models we adopted the same level of theory, and therefore the same real PES already employed for AH calculations.^{27,29} This choice allows us to use AH predictions as reference data to compare the different VH models in detail, considering frequencies, shapes of the normal modes, Duschinsky matrices, and both high-resolution (0 K) and room-temperature spectra. Comparison with experiments, already reported for these molecules for VH and AH models in Cartesian coordinates in previous papers,^{27,29} was given for completeness in the Supporting Information for all the systems except β -carotene to which we devote

a specific section of the manuscript. In fact, the new results in internal curvilinear coordinates lead us to partially revisit the conclusions we drove in ref. 29 stimulating us to also test the predictions of different functionals.

This work is organized as follows. First, Section 2, provides the required theoretical background for VH model in \mathbf{s} -frame while, for the sake of brevity, its comparison with VH models in different coordinate frames is given in the Supporting Information (SI). In Section 3 we summarize the adopted computational methods. Then, in the Section 4, we apply the presented vertical models to the calculation of the spectra of a set of benchmark molecules and compare the results with the adiabatic model. Finally, in Section 5, we summarize the main conclusions of this work.

2 Theoretical background

2.1 Internal coordinates description

Valence internal coordinates (bonds, angles and dihedrals) have some advantages over the Cartesian frame to deal with molecular vibrations, namely, they provide, by definition, the exact geometric separation of the rotation and translation degrees of freedom and are better suited to describe molecular vibrations. Such features make them a very convenient choice to describe the PES in a variety of applications, including geometry optimizations,^{41–45} reaction path dynamics,^{46–48} and vibrational spectroscopy.^{49,50} On the other side, they are non-orthogonal and the curvilinear nature of angles and dihedrals makes the dependence of valence internal (\mathbf{s}) on Cartesian coordinates (\mathbf{x}) complicated. It can be expressed as a Taylor expansion around a relevant structure \mathbf{x}_0 as follows,

$$\mathbf{s}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{s}_0 + \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0) + \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0)^t \boldsymbol{\beta}(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_0) + \dots \quad (2)$$

In the above expression we can identify the coefficients of each term as $\mathbf{s}_0 = \mathbf{s}(\mathbf{x}_0)$, $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{s}'(\mathbf{x}_0)$, $\boldsymbol{\beta} = \mathbf{s}''(\mathbf{x}_0)$, where the primes indicate derivatives with respect to Cartesian coordinates. In first-order approximation, we can define the so-called linearised internal coordinates, \mathbf{S} , discarding the terms beyond the linear one.

The \mathbf{B} matrix has a dimension ($N_s \times 3N_{at}$), where N_{at} is the number of atoms, and N_s is the number of internal coordinates (a non redundant set for non-linear and linear molecules has size $3N_{at} - 6$ or $3N_{at} - 5$, respectively). Its properties were investigated in detail in the seminal work by Wilson, Decius and Cross,⁵⁰ who derived analytical expressions for each of its terms in the case of bonds, angles and both proper and improper dihedrals.

By construction, the energy gradient is equivalent in the linearised and curvilinear valence internal coordinates, and it can be related to the one in Cartesian

coordinates, or mass-weighted Cartesian (mwc) coordinates, $\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{M}^{1/2}\mathbf{x}$ (\mathbf{M} being a diagonal matrix with triplets of nuclear masses as elements), by a linear transformation,

$$\mathbf{g}_x = \mathbf{B}^t \mathbf{g}_s \quad (3a)$$

$$\mathbf{g}_q = \mathbf{M}^{-1/2} \mathbf{B}^t \mathbf{g}_s \quad (3b)$$

where \mathbf{g}_x , \mathbf{g}_q and \mathbf{g}_s are column vectors.

Quantum Chemistry codes usually provide the energy gradient in terms of Cartesian coordinates. In order to obtain the gradient in internal coordinates, it is therefore necessary to invert the transformation in Eqs. 3a or 3b. As commented before, the \mathbf{B} matrix is not necessarily squared, thus, the opposite relation is found invoking the following expression,^{41,44}

$$\mathbf{g}_s = (\mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}\mathbf{B}^t)^+ \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}\mathbf{g}_x \quad (4)$$

where the superscript $+$ indicates the pseudo-inverse or generalized inverse⁴⁴ and \mathbf{u} is an arbitrary non-singular matrix⁴¹ which is customary taken as either the identity matrix or the diagonal matrix with the triplets of the inverse nuclear masses,⁴⁹ \mathbf{M}^{-1} . Note that the latter choice reduces to taking the Moore-Penrose pseudo-inverse^{51,52} of $(\mathbf{M}^{-1/2}\mathbf{B}^t)$ in the transformation between the gradient in internal and mass-weighted Cartesian coordinates, i.e., the ones in which the Eckart-Sayvetz conditions are defined.^{53,54} Concretely, $\mathbf{g}_s = (\mathbf{M}^{-1/2}\mathbf{B}^t)^+ \mathbf{g}_q = (\mathbf{M}^{-1/2}\mathbf{B}^t)^+ \mathbf{M}^{-1/2} \mathbf{g}_x$, where, for matrices with a rank equal to the number of columns, the pseudo inverse is defined as $\mathbf{W}^+ = (\mathbf{W}^t \mathbf{W})^{-1} \mathbf{W}$, where here $\mathbf{W} = (\mathbf{M}^{-1/2}\mathbf{B}^t)$. By setting $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{M}^{-1}$ and introducing the \mathbf{G} matrix, $\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{M}^{-1}\mathbf{B}$, the above expression can be recast as follows,

$$\mathbf{g}_s = \mathbf{G}^+ \mathbf{B}\mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{g}_x \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{G}^+ is the generalized-inverse of \mathbf{G} . If a non-redundant set of internal coordinates is used, \mathbf{G} is directly invertible and $\mathbf{G}^+ = \mathbf{G}^{-1}$, otherwise \mathbf{G}^+ is determined by diagonalizing \mathbf{G} and inverting its non-zero eigenvalues only.⁴⁴

Further deriving the gradient in Eq. 3a, the Hessian in Cartesian coordinates is obtained in terms of that in valence internal coordinates,

$$\mathbf{H}_x = \mathbf{B}^t \mathbf{H}_s \mathbf{B} + \mathbf{g}_s^t \boldsymbol{\beta} \quad (6)$$

where in this case, the coefficients of the second-order terms in the Taylor expansion in Eq. 2 arise and, consequently, the Hessian in linearised internal coordinates is

not equal to that in the curvilinear internal frame, $\mathbf{H}_S \neq \mathbf{H}_s$. The $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ term is a rank-3 array whose elements correspond to:

$$\beta_{ijk} = \frac{\partial s_i}{\partial x_j \partial x_k} \quad (7)$$

which can be evaluated analytically.^{45,55}

The inverse relation from Eq. 6 is obtained similarly to that of the gradient, leading to,⁴⁴

$$\mathbf{H}_s = \mathbf{G}^+ \mathbf{B} \mathbf{M}^{-1} (\mathbf{H}_x - \mathbf{g}_s^t \boldsymbol{\beta}) \mathbf{M}^{-1} \mathbf{B}^t \mathbf{G}^+ \quad (8)$$

As pointed out by Truhlar and co-workers,⁴⁷ the harmonic frequencies are affected by the choice of \mathbf{u} in Eq. 4 and when it is taken as \mathbf{M}^{-1} the Eckart-Sayvetz conditions^{53,54} are satisfied. In some test cases at stationary points, we confirmed that only taking \mathbf{u} as the inverse mass matrix, we could reproduce the frequencies computed with the usual procedure in mass-weighted Cartesian coordinates⁵⁰ that is discussed in Section 2.2.2, while other choices, such as the identity matrix led to slightly different results.

The use of the generalized inverse of the \mathbf{G} matrix used in Eq. 8, allow the use of redundant internal coordinates, which will eventually lead to a number of zero frequencies corresponding to the redundancies. In this work, we have followed an equivalent treatment, by first generating of a non-redundant set as linear combination of the original coordinates. As described by Reimers,³⁰ the rotation from the redundant to the non-redundant set can be obtained from the eigenvector matrix that diagonalizes the redundant \mathbf{G} matrix, discarding the eigenvectors that correspond to zero eigenvalues, which correspond to the redundancies. Such rotation is also applied to the \mathbf{B} matrix and its derivatives, $\boldsymbol{\beta}$.

2.2 Vertical approaches for FC spectra

The most problematic step in the calculation of the spectra under the VH approach is the vibrational analysis of the final state, since, in general it must be performed at a non-stationary point of the PES. In this section we report the derivation using curvilinear internal coordinates (\mathbf{s} -space) in order to highlight that two alternative options are possible to simplify the kinetic operator and define the final state normal modes. Moreover we briefly discuss the difference of the model in \mathbf{s} -space with respect to those obtained within alternative frames (like Cartesian coordinates \mathbf{x}). A more detailed comparison is given in the Supporting Information (SI).

2.2.1 Internal coordinates (\mathbf{s} -space)

In internal non-redundant coordinates the kinetic (T)⁵⁰ and potential (V) energies at a generic non-stationary point are

$$2T = \dot{\mathbf{s}}^t \mathbf{G}^{-1}(\mathbf{s}) \dot{\mathbf{s}} \quad (9)$$

$$2V = \mathbf{s}^t \mathbf{H}_s \mathbf{s} + 2\mathbf{g}_s^t \mathbf{s} + 2V_0 \quad (10)$$

where we adopted a local harmonic approximation (LHA) for the PES and we wrote explicitly the dependence of \mathbf{G} on the internal coordinates. One route to solve the equations of motion in Lagrangian form⁵⁰

$$\frac{d}{dt} \frac{\partial T}{\partial \dot{s}_i} + \frac{\partial V}{\partial s_i} = 0 \quad (i = 1, N_{vib}) \quad (11)$$

is to first locate the minimum of the LHA of the potential

$$\Delta \mathbf{s} = -\mathbf{H}_s^{-1} \mathbf{g}_s \quad (12)$$

and then apply a translation of the coordinates $\mathbf{s}' \rightarrow (\mathbf{s} - \Delta \mathbf{s})$. The expression for T and V becomes

$$2T = \dot{\mathbf{s}}'^t \mathbf{G}^{-1}(\mathbf{s}) \dot{\mathbf{s}}' \quad (13)$$

$$2V = \mathbf{s}'^t \mathbf{H}_s \mathbf{s}' \quad (14)$$

To proceed further, it is customary⁵⁰ to expand \mathbf{G} in Taylor series and retain only the constant term $\mathbf{G} \sim \mathbf{G}(\Delta \mathbf{s}) = \mathbf{G}_{eq}$, where the *eq* subscript recalls that \mathbf{G} is now taken at the equilibrium position of the LHA of the final PES. This allows to obtain the usual GF equations⁵⁰

$$\mathbf{G}_{eq} \mathbf{H}_s \mathbf{L}_s = \mathbf{L}_s \mathbf{\Lambda} \quad (15)$$

where \mathbf{L}_s represents the normal modes in internal coordinates and $\mathbf{\Lambda}$ is the diagonal force constant matrix.

The above expression can be recast into a more convenient eigenvalue problem by orthogonalizing the internal coordinates, which involves a non-unitary transformation, $\mathbf{s}'_o = \mathbf{G}_{eq}^{-1/2} \mathbf{s}'$, leading to,

$$\mathbf{F}_{so} \mathbf{L}_{so} = \mathbf{L}_{so} \mathbf{\Lambda} \quad (16)$$

where \mathbf{F}_{so} and \mathbf{L}_{so} are the Hessian and normal modes in the orthogonal internal frame. Notice that since \mathbf{G} was made independent of the coordinates and substituted by \mathbf{G}_{eq} , \mathbf{F}_{so} can be simply obtained as

$$\mathbf{F}_{so} = \mathbf{G}_{eq}^{1/2} \mathbf{H}_s \mathbf{G}_{eq}^{1/2}, \quad (17)$$

i.e. no additional term depending on the derivative of the transformation to the orthogonal set appears in Eq. 17.

The normal mode matrices in internal and orthogonalized internal coordinates are simply related by $\mathbf{L}_s = \mathbf{G}_{eq}^{1/2} \mathbf{L}_{so}$. For the initial state the expansion of the PES is performed at a stationary point and therefore the procedure is simpler since the terms depending on the gradient are zero in Eqs. 8 and 9. Finally, we have for initial (1) and final (2) states,

$$\mathbf{s} = \mathbf{G}_{1,eq}^{1/2} \mathbf{L}_{1,so} \mathbf{Q}_1 \quad (18)$$

$$\mathbf{s} - \Delta \mathbf{s} = \mathbf{G}_{2,eq}^{1/2} \mathbf{L}_{2,so} \mathbf{Q}_2 \quad (19)$$

where the subscripts highlight that the $\mathbf{G}_{1,eq}$ and $\mathbf{G}_{2,eq}$ matrices are in principle different since the first is taken at the exact equilibrium geometry of the initial state and the second at the (approximate) equilibrium geometry of the final state estimated within the LHA through Eq. 12. Simple algebra leads to the definition of the Duschinsky matrix and the displacement vector as,

$$\mathbf{J} = \mathbf{L}_{s,1}^{-1} \mathbf{L}_{s,2} = \mathbf{L}_{so,1}^{-1} \mathbf{G}_{1,eq}^{-1/2} \mathbf{G}_{2,eq}^{1/2} \mathbf{L}_{so,2} \quad (20)$$

$$\mathbf{K} = \mathbf{L}_{s,1}^{-1} \Delta \mathbf{s} = -\mathbf{L}_{s,1}^{-1} \mathbf{H}_s^{-1} \mathbf{g}_s. \quad (21)$$

In summary, in order to retain the simplicity of the GF method and define initial- and final-state normal modes it is necessary to assume that \mathbf{G} is independent of the nuclear coordinates. For the initial state, \mathbf{G} is taken equal to $\mathbf{G}_{1,eq}$, i.e. its value at the equilibrium structure of the state. For the final state, two different strategies are possible. The first one, is the one described above and, in line with the standard GF procedure,⁵⁰ it involves locating the minimum of the LHA of the final PES and evaluating there the \mathbf{G} matrix, i.e. fixing it to the value $\mathbf{G}_{2,eq}$ matrix. This however makes the \mathbf{J} matrix dependent on $\mathbf{G}_{1,eq}^{-1/2} \mathbf{G}_{2,eq}^{1/2}$. Notice that the expression for \mathbf{J} in Eq. 20 is actually analogous to what obtained for adiabatic approaches, and may encounter the same non-orthogonality problems.²⁹ In line with the philosophy of the vertical approach, where all the quantities to compute the spectra are expanded around the initial-state geometry, a second strategy can be invoked, assigning to \mathbf{G} the value $\mathbf{G}_{1,eq}$ also for the final state. This choice corresponds to substitute $\mathbf{G}_{1,eq}$ to $\mathbf{G}_{2,eq}$ in the previous equations and has the benefit to make the computational protocol simpler since the Duschinsky matrix becomes an orthogonal transformation $\mathbf{J} = \mathbf{L}_{so,1}^t \mathbf{L}_{so,2}$.

In our opinion, for the scope to build a VH model no strong argument can be invoked to prefer one of the two assumptions for the \mathbf{G} matrix of the final

state, namely $\mathbf{G}_{1,eq}$ or $\mathbf{G}_{2,eq}$, since such choice will influence (and not in a simple way) the whole shape of the vibrational wavefunctions of the final-state, therefore both in the FC region and in the region of the PES minimum. Therefore when the two choices lead to predict significantly different spectral shapes, one should consider more refined treatments that explicitly account for \mathbf{G} dependence on \mathbf{s} . This would however introduce couplings between coordinates and momenta which prevent easy solutions in terms of separable normal modes, requiring the explicit adoption of the quantum Hamiltonian, as it was done in ref. 56, a strategy that is not viable for systems with dozens of vibrational coordinates.

2.2.2 Comparison of linear and curvilinear coordinates

In contrast to the methodology presented in the previous section, most of the formulations of the vertical model in the last years have been based on linear coordinates, such as the Cartesian (or mass-weighted Cartesian, MWC) coordinates and the linearised internal coordinates,³² or also the normal mode coordinates of the initial state expressed in terms of Cartesian coordinates.²⁷ As we discuss in more detail in the SI, all these coordinate systems can be regarded as linear transformations of a given coordinate set, e.g. the Cartesian one \mathbf{x} , and therefore they all provide the same results for the normal mode analysis.

The difference between the adoption of linear and curvilinear coordinates reside on the Hessian matrix evaluated at non-stationary points. A convenient comparison can be made by considering as a basis set the normal modes in the initial state, \mathbf{Q}_1 , since they can both be described as linear or non-linear combinations of the set \mathbf{x} (obtaining in the latter case the so-called curvilinear normal modes which are actually taken as linear combinations of the curvilinear set \mathbf{s}).⁵⁶ In the linear (*lin*) case ($\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_{0,1} = \mathbf{M}^{-1/2}\mathbf{L}_1\mathbf{Q}_1^{(lin)}$, where $\mathbf{x}_{0,1}$ is the equilibrium position of the initial state), the Hessian matrix of the final state can be expressed in terms of the Cartesian Hessian as,

$$\mathbf{H}_{Q_1^{(lin)}} = \mathbf{L}_1^t \mathbf{M}^{-1/2} (\mathbf{H}_x) \mathbf{M}^{-1/2} \mathbf{L}_1 \quad (22)$$

On the contrary, the analogous expression in curvilinear (*curv*) normal modes ($\mathbf{s} - \mathbf{s}_{0,1} = \mathbf{L}_{s,1}\mathbf{Q}_1^{(curv)}$) is equivalent to that reported in Eq. 8 for curvilinear valence internal coordinates and is given by,

$$\mathbf{H}_{Q_1^{(curv)}} = \mathbf{L}_1^t \mathbf{M}^{-1/2} (\mathbf{H}_x - \mathbf{g}_s^t \boldsymbol{\beta}) \mathbf{M}^{-1/2} \mathbf{L}_1 \quad (23)$$

It is evident that the additional term in the case of curvilinear internal coordinates, $\mathbf{g}_s^t \boldsymbol{\beta}$, will lead to a different normal mode analysis with respect to linear coordinates at non-stationary points.

Figure 1: Molecular structures of all compounds studied in this work: anthracene (**I**), coumarin C153 (**II**), free-base porphyrin (**III**), pyrazine (**IV**), uracil (**V**) and 6,6'-dicis β -carotene (**VI**).

3 Computational methods

We apply the methodologies reviewed in Section 2 to a set of paradigmatic cases, for which we already simulated the electronic absorption spectra within the VH model in the $\mathbf{Q}_1^{(lin)}$ -frame, equivalent to the \mathbf{x} -frame since the $\mathbf{Q}_1^{(lin)}$ coordinates were considered a linear combination of the Cartesian coordinates.^{27,29} The first two molecules, anthracene (**I**) and coumarin C153 (**II**) were chosen as examples of rigid systems for which harmonic approximation works well.²⁷ Free base porphyrin (**III**) was selected because it is rigid but, at variance with **I** and **II**, also shows important Herzberg-Teller effects, and pyrazine (**IV**) and uracil (**V**) as examples of molecules where imaginary frequencies in the excited PES reflect true characteristics of the systems, and therefore occur on both adiabatic and vertical models. Finally, system (**VI**), β -carotene, was included to show a case where due to remarkable curvilinear displacements both AH and VH models within the \mathbf{s} -frame shows limitations. All the investigated systems are sketched in Figure 1.

The molecules **I-VI** were optimized in the ground (GS) and first excited (ES) states (except **V** that is optimized in the second excited state) adopting DFT and TDDFT methods respectively, using the Gaussian09 program.⁵⁷ In keeping

with our previous studies, the PBE0 functional was used for all the molecules and, for **VI**, also CAM-B3LYP. In all cases, the 6-31G(d) basis was employed. The GS Hessian at GS minimum and the ES Hessian at the ES and GS minima were computed at the same level of theory. For **IV** and **V** ES optimizations were performed in the point-group symmetry of the GS, respectively D_{2h} and C_s .

The lineshape of absorption electronic spectra are computed within harmonic approximation using TI and TD strategies as implemented in the development version of our code *FCclasses*.^{58,59} In the TI approach, the lineshape, $L(\omega)$, is evaluated through the sum over all individual transitions from the thermally populated vibrational level ($|\mathbf{v}_1\rangle$) in the initial (1) electronic state ($|\mathbf{e}_1\rangle$) to those ($|\mathbf{v}_2\rangle$) in the final (2) electronic state ($|\mathbf{e}_2\rangle$),⁵

$$L(\omega) = \sum_{v_1, v_2} \rho_{v_1}(T) |\langle \mathbf{v}_1 | \boldsymbol{\mu}_{12} | \mathbf{v}_2 \rangle|^2 \delta(\omega_{v_2} - \omega_{v_1} \pm (\Delta E/\hbar - \omega)) \quad (24)$$

where the plus and minus symbols hold for absorption and emission respectively, ρ_{v_1} is the Boltzmann population of the vibrational state $|\mathbf{v}_1\rangle$, ΔE the adiabatic energy difference between the minima of ES and GS PESs, and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{12}$ (3-dimensional column vector) is the electronic transition dipole moment. Efficient prescreening techniques exists to evaluate the above expression,^{1,3,60,61} and we adopt the one implemented in our code.⁶⁰

In the TD framework, the lineshape is obtained from the Fourier transform of the finite-temperature time correlation function, $\chi(t, T)$ ^{6,8} as follows

$$L(\omega) = \frac{1}{2\pi Z_{v_1}} \int \chi(t, T) e^{\mp it(\Delta E/\hbar - \omega)} dt \quad (25)$$

where Z_{v_1} is the vibrational partition function of the initial states, $|\mathbf{v}_1\rangle$. The analytical expression of the correlation function has been derived by different groups including FC and HT terms.^{7-12,15,62} We use the one implemented in the development version of our code.¹³

The displacement vector and Duschinsky matrix required to carry out the simulations were computed according to the AH²⁷ model as well as the VH one using, in the latter case, the methods reviewed in the previous section. The second derivatives of the internal coordinates with respect to the Cartesian ones, i.e., the elements of the $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ array, were derived starting from the analytical expressions for the first derivatives (\mathbf{B} matrix). Concretely, they were evaluated analytically through the *sympy* Python library and then implemented in Fortran codes. Their correctness was double-checked by comparison with numerical derivatives which revealed very stable and precise. The AH model was formulated in Cartesian coordinates, except in the case of molecule **VI**, where internal coordinates were also used, referring to it as AH(I). In all the cases, the displacements and Duschinsky matrix were obtained using a program developed locally. In the following we present

VH results in Cartesian (VH(C)) and curvilinear internal coordinates (VH(I)). As mentioned in Section 2, VH models in the Cartesian \mathbf{x} frame are equivalent to those in the \mathbf{Q}_1 frame, if \mathbf{Q}_1 modes are expressed as linear combinations of Cartesian coordinates. Results obtained using curvilinear internal coordinates (\mathbf{s} -frame) are instead equivalent to those obtainable in a \mathbf{Q}_1 -frame where \mathbf{Q}_1 coordinates are taken as linear combinations of \mathbf{s} ones.

Except otherwise stated, the transition dipole moment was described within FC approximation, i.e., it was assumed to be independent on the normal mode coordinates. For **III**, some calculations are also performed including the HT terms, using the numerical first derivatives of the transition dipole moment computed at the geometry of the initial state (FCHT₁) or final state (FCHT₂).²⁷

4 Results and discussion

4.1 Vibrational analysis at non-stationary points in Cartesian and internal coordinates

In order to perform a vibrational analysis in curvilinear internal coordinates a set of valence coordinates must be selected and related to Cartesian coordinates by a second-order Taylor expansion, which is enough to exactly compute the Hessian. The biggest issue of internal coordinates is that they are not orthogonal and that \mathbf{G} matrix that enters the kinetic energy term depends on the internal coordinates. As mentioned in Section 2, following a “vertical philosophy”, we consider it constant and, as a standard, we set it to the value it has at the vertical point ($\mathbf{G}_{1,eq}$) for the analysis in the final state PES. Such a choice is also more straightforward to apply than the alternative approximate protocol, where the constant \mathbf{G} is set equal to its value at the minimum of the quadratic ES PES, $\mathbf{G}_{2,eq}$. In that case, the minimum should be located using Eq. 12, a step that may meet some complications when converting the shifts from internal to Cartesian coordinates.^{41,44,45} Moreover, the normal mode analysis on the final state is not very much affected by the choice of either $\mathbf{G}_{1,eq}$ or $\mathbf{G}_{2,eq}$ approaches for the systems under study (details in the SI for the interested reader).

The set of internal valence coordinates is, in principle, arbitrary, as far as it spans the whole vibrational space. In this sense, a non-redundant set can be generated, for instance, from either the so-called Z-matrix or, more in general, from linear combinations of any appropriate redundant set (i.e. spanning the whole vibrational space), as the one containing all bonds, angles and dihedrals that arise from the connectivity pattern. However, as already noted by Truhlar and co-workers,⁴⁷ the different non-redundant sets will not necessarily provide equivalent descriptions of the harmonic PES at non-stationary points. Interestingly, such non-equivalence can also be traced back to the different performance of the Z-matrix and redundant sets in the context of structural optimization algorithms.⁴⁴

Table 1: Lowest and highest frequencies (cm^{-1}) computed for molecules **I** and **II** on the vertical point of the ES in Cartesian (V(C)) and internal (V(I)) coordinates with different sets of valence internal coordinates: all internal arising from connectivity (I-a), from an arbitrary Z-matrix (I-z).

	I ($N_v = 66$)			II ($N_v = 102$)		
	V(C)	V(I-a)	V(I-z)	V(C)	V(I-a)	V(I-z)
1	$75i$	90	$216i$	$99i$	29	$255i$
2	140	112	$108i$	$41i$	47	$62i$
3	157	237	$70i$	34	51	23
4	228	240	73	71	75	49
$N_v - 3$	3224	3224	3224	3142	3142	3142
$N_v - 2$	3225	3224	3224	3151	3151	3151
$N_v - 1$	3236	3237	3236	3244	3244	3244
N_v	3238	3238	3238	3289	3289	3289

Mathematically, the differences can be easily highlighted when the system has a certain molecular symmetry at the vertical point, assuming that the Hessian should remain unchanged with respect to the application of any symmetry operation of the molecule. As we discuss in the Supporting Information (SI), for this condition to be met by the Hessian in internal coordinates, the term $(\mathbf{g}_s^t \boldsymbol{\beta})$ must be invariant to these symmetry operations, a condition that is always guaranteed with all internal coordinates but not with the Z-matrix.

A clear evidence of the above discussion is given by the frequency analysis in curvilinear internal coordinates, using either the Z-matrix or all internal coordinates derived from the connectivity pattern. In Table 1, the frequencies obtained with each internal set are shown for molecules **I** and **II**, which turn out to be highly dependent on the selected set of coordinates. For instance, for molecule **I**, the use of the Z-matrix lead to 3 imaginary frequencies, while only real values are obtained when the redundant set of all coordinates is used. As we will see in the next section, the latter result is much more reasonable. Taking into account the symmetry of this molecule, we confirmed that, when the Z-matrix is used, the $(\mathbf{g}_s^t \boldsymbol{\beta})$ term is not invariant with respect to the symmetry operations, while it is invariant if the set including all internal coordinates is used, instead. Nevertheless, a similar behaviour is also found in molecule **II**, without symmetry, indicating that the better performance of the set including all coordinates is somehow a more general trend. It is also remarkable that the differences are mainly localized on low-frequency modes.

Moreover, it is further observed in Table 1 that, also the use of Cartesian coordinates can lead to unphysical imaginary frequencies for low-frequency modes. Therefore, curvilinear internal coordinates (using the set of all internal coordinates arising from connectivity) is the preferable set to perform the vibrational analysis

at non stationary points. This finding was also noted by Truhlar and collaborators⁴⁶ in the context of intrinsic reaction paths. The superior performance of internal coordinates is connected to their curvilinear nature, which has the advantage of avoiding the contamination of pseudo-rotations that takes place with Cartesian coordinates at non-stationary points.⁶³ Such effect is confirmed by noticing that, at non-stationary points, the modes associated to the pseudo-rotations get non-zero values, as expected by theory,⁶³⁻⁶⁵ and, parallel to this, the vibrational frequencies evaluated with Cartesian coordinates deviate from the values obtained at the equilibrium geometry, as we show in the SI.

The improved performance of curvilinear coordinates is related with the fact that they are a better basis to describe molecular motions, and this makes them more suited to describe the PES with a low order expansion, as the harmonic approximation. Nevertheless, as already stated by Truhlar and co-workers, if we could account for “anharmonic corrections and vibrational-rotation coupling to infinite order, the choice of coordinate system (...) would not affect the accuracy”.⁴⁷

4.2 Harmonic PESs with vertical and adiabatic models

In this section we compare the model ES PES obtained by application of either the vertical (in Cartesian and internal coordinates) or the adiabatic approaches. We start computing the ES frequencies for the six molecules in Figure 1. In Table 2 we report the lowest frequencies computed at the minimum (adiabatic, A) and FC geometry (vertical, V). In the latter case, the frequencies are computed adopting either Cartesian, V(C), or internal, V(I), coordinates, which, as shown in the previous section, can provide quite different results, especially for low-frequency modes. In the adiabatic case, however, any set of coordinates provide exactly the same frequency analysis, since the latter is performed at a stationary point.

As observed in this table, the frequencies computed with V(I) are generally more similar to those computed with the adiabatic model. Remarkably, for some molecules, V(C) sometimes exhibits imaginary frequencies that do not have a counterpart in the adiabatic model. On the contrary, V(I) always provides the same number of imaginary frequencies predicted in an adiabatic calculation. For **I**, **II**, **III** and **VI**, the adiabatic model shows no imaginary frequencies and the V(I) model predicts frequencies very similar to the adiabatic ones. The structures of **IV** and **V** in the ES were optimized retaining the symmetry of the GS state, and some imaginary frequencies arise in the A model. In these cases, V models are able to provide the same number of imaginary frequencies, although the values change significantly. Concretely, for **IV**, the imaginary frequency in the A model is nearly double as compared to that obtained with V(I). It should be taken into account that such imaginary frequencies are usually related to DW profiles, which are strongly anharmonic and, therefore, the second derivative can change drastically from the minimum to the FC point. The situation becomes even more problematic for the considered S₂ state of **V**, where the fourth frequency, which is real, changes

Table 2: Lowest frequencies (in cm^{-1}) computed at the excited state modelled with the vertical approach in Cartesian (V(C)) and internal (V(I)) formulations, and the adiabatic one (A) for the six molecules treated in this work. In the adiabatic case, both internal and Cartesian formulations provide identical results.

	I			II			III		
	V(C)	V(I)	A	V(C)	V(I)	A	V(C)	V(I)	A
1	75 <i>i</i>	90	89	99 <i>i</i>	29	28	40	53	52
2	140	112	112	41 <i>i</i>	47	48	45	64	64
3	157	237	232	34	51	54	94	96	97
4	228	240	239	71	75	72	98	103	98
5	257	248	251	84	94	95	116	122	121
6	293	330	330	104	116	110	125	127	127
7	375	384	382	112	119	121	151	154	152
8	400	402	397	138	141	142	171	183	181
9	420	422	419	157	192	195	195	198	197
10	439	439	439	193	202	199	195	202	203
11	500	517	513	195	237	234	276	288	286
12	517	517	521	263	266	265	288	293	288
13	519	535	533	264	267	269	311	313	310
14	593	604	599	295	297	291	312	315	311
15	594	607	602	309	309	310	312	319	317
	IV			V			VI		
	V(C)	V(I)	A	V(C)	V(I)	A	V(C)	V(I)	A
1	214 <i>i</i>	277 <i>i</i>	502 <i>i</i>	337 <i>i</i>	348 <i>i</i>	377 <i>i</i>	34 <i>i</i>	5	5
2	214	258	243	168 <i>i</i>	182 <i>i</i>	129 <i>i</i>	28 <i>i</i>	9	9
3	430	413	442	89	163	175	5 <i>i</i>	14	14
4	472	461	488	173	194	306	7	16	14
5	493	518	510	311	358	334	16	24	23
6	613	628	602	367	374	437	21	28	28
7	628	651	618	409	445	451	22	34	34
8	702	708	702	438	471	515	40	42	43
9	770	727	740	491	531	546	42	46	46
10	855	829	829	520	535	563	46	54	52
11	877	851	849	549	584	689	55	54	55
12	1063	1062	1041	640	676	729	57	68	70
13	1089	1089	1052	737	759	760	70	76	77
14	1091	1089	1097	757	783	822	77	81	85
15	1238	1237	1213	856	859	886	85	87	92

from 306 cm^{-1} with the A model, to 194 cm^{-1} according to V(I). Also in this case, the flexibility of the cycle in the ES can be associated with remarkable anharmonic effects, possibly explaining large difference between V and A models. Moreover, it has been documented that the nature itself of the $S_2 \pi\pi^*$ transition of **V** can partially change from the GS to the ES minima,⁶⁶ and this can clearly induce a change of the ES frequencies in the two points.

The data in Table 2 agree with the observations of Truhlar and co-workers,^{47,48} who showed, in the context of the formulation of the intrinsic reaction coordinate in curvilinear internal coordinates, that the frequencies computed with Cartesian coordinates at non-stationary points might be inaccurate, while internal coordinates provide more realistic values. In our study, which deals with the simulation of vibronic spectra, we are interested not only in the values of the frequencies, but also in the shape of the modes themselves, which should be also compared between the vertical and adiabatic models. Such a comparison can be performed by projecting the modes computed in the vertical point, with both coordinate systems, onto the adiabatic modes. Ideally, assuming that the modes provided by each model are identical, the projection matrix would be the identity matrix.

Plots in the SI show to the interested reader that for low-frequency modes, deviations from the identity matrix are significantly larger when they are described in Cartesian coordinates. On the other hand, the results for medium- to high-frequency modes are very similar with both vertical formulations. Namely, for medium-frequency modes some differences usually arise between A and V models, which can be related to anharmonic effects, while a good one-to-one mapping is observed for modes with larger frequencies (i.e. C-H stretchings).

The inaccurate description on the low frequency V(C) modes can introduce additional vibrational transitions in the final spectrum. The extent of this effect can be evidenced by computing the fictitious spectrum from the adiabatic to the vertical model PES of the ES. For the following analysis, we focus on **I** and **II** since, due to their rigidity, the harmonic approximation is expected to be accurate and therefore A and V models should deliver similar descriptions of the ES PES. In the limiting case in which the PES were exactly identical, they would share the same vibrational wavefunctions and, assuming that only the ground state is populated, all transitions (FC factors) would be negligible, except for the 0-0 transition, which would be equal to one. In Figure 2, we show the actual FC factors obtained for the transition $\text{ES(A)} \rightarrow \text{ES(V)}$, and more precisely from the ground vibrational state of ES(A) to all the vibrational states of ES(V), for molecules **I** and **II**. In both systems, the transition to V(I) modes is closer to the ideal situation, as compared with the transition to V(C) ones. This effect can be traced back to a better matching of both frequencies, which reduce the overtones due to the frequency shifts, and modes, which reduce couplings and, consequently, the number of combination bands. For **II**, for which V(C) predicts two imaginary frequencies, arbitrarily transformed into real by taking their absolute value, the effect is even more pronounced, as the FC factor of the 0-0 transition goes from

Figure 2: Franck-Condon factors arising from the transition of the adiabatic to the vertical model PESs in the ES for molecules **I** and **II**. Both Cartesian and internal coordinates are used with the vertical model. The 0-0 transition is shown in black, overtones in blue and combination bands in red.

~ 0.7 with V(C) to ~ 0.9 with V(I).

4.3 Simulation of electronic lineshapes

In this section we compare the vibronic structures of the absorption spectra of molecules **I-VI** predicted by VH(C) and VH(I) models with those obtained with the AH one. The results depend on the different Duschinsky matrices predicted by these models, which are graphically represented in the SI for all the molecules. In general, similar Duschinsky matrices are computed for the AH and VH(I) models, while in the case of VH(C), additional couplings arise between the GS and ES low frequency modes, as a consequence of the poor description of these modes with V(C) model discussed above.

Let us first focus on the spectra for the rigid molecules **I** to **III**, which are included in Figure 3. Note that in all cases, the VH(C) and VH(I) spectra are

shifted to match the first band of the reference AH ones. In general, the difference between the VH(C) and VH(I) approaches are mainly observed at high temperatures, indicating their different behaviour against temperature anticipated above. It is clearly observed that although both VH approaches and the AH one deliver similar results at 0 K, VH(I) keeps better the similarities with AH at high temperatures, while the VH(C) model results in a partial loss of resolution of the vibronic peaks and a larger broadening.

We emphasize that the application of the VH(C) model for molecules **I** and **II** lead to spurious imaginary frequencies, that were turned to real values by simply taking their absolute value. Such a protocol is certainly arbitrary and, especially at high temperatures, the lineshape may be drastically dependent on the selected values. This is shown in the SI assigning different frequencies to the problematic modes of **II**. Moreover, it is worthy to highlight that the bad description of the low frequency modes with the VH(C) model can affect the spectra even when no imaginary frequencies are obtained. A very good example of this behaviour is molecule **III** where VH(C) results remarkably deviate for VH(I) and AH predictions at room temperature. This is an effect of an overestimation of GS→ES changes of some harmonic frequencies and of the occurrence of additional couplings in the Duschinsky matrix.

The spectra in Figure 3 are computed adopting the FC approximation to account for the electronic transition dipole moment, which is suited to treat bright transitions. However, for molecule **III** the transition is rather weak and it is known to undergo large HT effects;^{27,60} therefore we have also computed the spectra including linear (HT) terms. For consistency, the linear HT expansion is performed at the geometry of the initial state (FCHT₁) for VH approaches and at the geometry of the final state (FCHT₂) for the AH model.²⁷ The spectra are presented in Figure 4 and show that differences between A and V approaches are very similar to those observed for FC spectra: all AH, VH(C) and VH(I) provide a similar lineshape at 0 K, while VH(C) leads to significant differences at 300 K due to larger temperature effects. Finally, we remark here that, in general, VH(I) spectra are slightly blue-shifted with respect to AH and VH(C) spectra, an effect that is more clearly identified for molecule **III** due to the energy scale. This discrepancy arises from the fact that, in general, the vertical frequencies are slightly larger as compared with the adiabatic ones, which lead to a larger 0-0 transition energy (further details in the SI for the interested reader). These differences are less visible in VH(C) because the erroneous lower frequencies tend to compensate the differences with the AH 0-0 energies. On the balance however, the spectra are rather similar; therefore since AH and VH(C) results compare nicely with experiment⁶⁷⁻⁶⁹ (apart from the underestimation of the 0-0 peak in **III**),²⁷ the same is true for VH(I) (SI).

We now turn to molecules **IV** and **V** whose spectra are reported in Figure 5. These systems are characterized by the occurrence of some imaginary frequencies in the ES PES that arise from the fact that it was optimized under D_{2h} and C_s

Figure 3: Lineshape spectra at 0 and 300K simulated with the AH model in Cartesian coordinates and the VH one in either Cartesian, VH(C), or internal, VH(I), coordinates for molecules **I** to **III**, evaluating the PESs with PBE0. The spectra are broadened by a Gaussian function with HWHM=0.01 eV.

Figure 4: Lineshape spectra of molecule **III** at 0 and 300 K simulated with the AH and VH (Cartesian and internal) models adopting the FCHT₁ and FCHT₂ approximations, respectively, to describe the transition dipole moment. PESs evaluated with PBE0. The spectra are broadened by a Gaussian function with HWHM=0.01 eV.

symmetry constraints, respectively; therefore they are observed with all adiabatic and vertical models. These frequencies reflect the tendency of the ES to remove some symmetry elements, creating DW potentials that are intrinsically anharmonic. In ref. 27 it was shown that for **IV** the DW profile does not sustain any bound vibrational state below the barrier and, the PES was simplified by performing a mono-dimensional scan and computing an effective frequency that turns to be $\sim 1030 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. We here followed the same strategy. A more refined treatment might involve the approach proposed by Hazra and Nooijen in ref. 40. As shown in Figure 5 small differences in the simulations of the spectra of **IV** with VH(C), AH and VH(I) models appear already at 0 K. It is remarkable in this case, that the spectra at 300 K display basically the same differences, which indicates that, in this case, the V(C) and V(I) models perform similarly (and therefore the comparison of V(I) results with experiment⁷⁰ do not differentiate substantially from what already discussed for AH and VH(C) in ref. 27(SI).

The case of molecule **V** is rather different as compared to molecules **I** to **IV**. As it was discussed in the previous section, the high-anharmonicity of the ES PES leads to large differences between the vertical and adiabatic ES modes. In such a complex scenario, we made the simplest possible approximation to simulate the

Figure 5: Lineshape spectra at 0 and 300K simulated with the AH model in Cartesian coordinates and the VH one in either Cartesian, VH(C), or internal, VH(I), coordinates for molecules **I** to **III**, evaluating the PESs with PBE0. For molecule **VI** the AH model in internal coordinates is also included. The spectra are broadened by a Gaussian function with $\text{HWHM}=0.01$ eV.

spectra, merely substituting the two imaginary frequencies, found in each model, by their absolute values. The simulated spectra are shown in Figure 5. As already shown in ref. 27, even at 0 K, VH(C) and AH spectra computed in this way are remarkably different, both considering their position and their width. The lineshapes are mainly a result of the different displacements along high-frequency modes and, consequently, they are mostly independent of the low-frequency ones that are potentially inaccurate in VH(C). This explains why VH(I) and VH(C) spectra are rather similar in this case also at 300 K. Therefore, as far as the comparison with experiment⁷¹ is concerned (see SI), the discussion is pretty analogous to what already reported in ref. 27 for VH(C) and AH models: the computations qualitatively reproduce the broad and structureless band observed in experiment, and the AH model makes a larger error on the absolute position. This happens because the harmonic PES expanded around the ES minimum predicts a vertical transition energy at the GS minimum that largely deviates from the true value computed by a single-point TD-DFT calculation.²⁷ Due to the complexity of the system, where the anharmonicity is partially intrinsic to the nature of the $\pi\pi^*$ state and partially due to the couplings with close-lying states,⁶⁶ more accurate simulations would require the adoption of different nonadiabatic and anharmonic approaches. In this sense, since the non-planar minimum of the $\pi\pi^*$ state is characterized by strong curvilinear displacements of the molecular ring, it is reasonable that curvilinear coordinates adopted in VH(I) will represent a better starting point to set up improved PES models.

The situation for the last molecule, **VI**, is quite particular. In this case, we showed in ref. 29 that in Cartesian coordinates the adiabatic model (AH(C)) completely fails, leading to an over-broadened spectrum, while the vertical model (VH(C)) delivers plausible spectra. The failure of the adiabatic model is cured using internal coordinates obtaining spectra with acceptable width but significantly different from VH(C) ones.²⁹ In the present work we discovered that, even adopting an internal set of coordinates, at high temperature vertical (VH(I)) and adiabatic (AH(I)) models still show very remarkable differences. In addition, this system shows relevant differences between the predictions of the $\mathbf{G}_{1,eq}$ and $\mathbf{G}_{2,eq}$ approximations of VH(I) model. These findings lead to revisit the comparison itself with experiment reported in ref. 29. Therefore, the case of this system is analysed in detail in the following subsection.

4.3.1 $\mathbf{G}_{1,eq}$ and $\mathbf{G}_{2,eq}$ approximations in VH(I) models. The case of β -carotene

Our default VH(I) protocol adopts the \mathbf{G} matrix evaluated at the initial state minimum structure ($\mathbf{G}_{1,eq}$) to carry out the vibrational analysis of the final state too, and it is the one used to simulate the spectra reported in Figures 3 to 5. In principle, such vibrational analysis may change if, on the contrary, \mathbf{G} matrix is evaluated at the minimum of the quadratic curve ($\mathbf{G}_{2,eq}$). In this sense, it is

important to check the impact on the final spectra of the choice of the value of the \mathbf{G} matrix, which is done by comparing the lineshapes obtained with the two possible strategies, the default $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{1,eq})$ and $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{2,eq})$.

The $\mathbf{G}_{2,eq}$ matrix is evaluated at the geometry of the final state quadratic curve, which is obtained with the iterative method adopted in Section 4.1 and described more in detail in the SI. This allows us to compute the Duschinsky matrix following Eq. 20 and subsequently to simulate the spectra as usual. The results for all molecules adopting both $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{1,eq})$ and $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{2,eq})$ strategies reveal that the spectra with both approaches are quite similar for all systems, except for **VI** (Figure S19 in the SI). This finding confirms the robustness of our results and points out that molecule **VI** deserves a specific attention.

Few years ago²⁹ we already investigated β -carotene showing that Cartesian coordinates are not suitable to describe the curvilinear displacements between the initial and final state equilibrium geometries, which is associated with the torsion of the C-C bond connecting the β -ionone ring with the conjugated chain. As a consequence, the AH model in Cartesian coordinates leads to an overestimation of the spectral width due to the couplings between torsional and C-H stretchings modes. At variance, both AH(I) and VH(C) were shown to provide more reasonable spectral shapes in better agreement with experiment. It should be however highlighted that the VH(C) calculations predicted two small imaginary frequencies at B3LYP/6-31G(d) level that were arbitrarily substituted by their absolute values.²⁹ In this contribution we reconsider the system by adopting the VH(I) model. It is noteworthy that VH(I) solves the problem of the spurious imaginary frequencies, which are three for VH(C) with PBE0 functional, predicting low frequencies extremely similar to the AH ones (Table 2). However, quite interestingly, it predicts a spectrum remarkably different from AH(I) and VH(C) at high temperatures (Figure 5). More specifically, both AH(I) and VH(C) exhibit very large temperature effects that are, however, not present in the VH(I) model.

Going in further detail, Figure 5 shows that for this molecule AH(I) and VH(C) spectra are similar, exhibiting the maximum at the second vibrational band (in order of increasing energy) at 300 K. $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{2,eq})$ results (top panel of Figure 6) are also similar, while $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{1,eq})$ ones are different since the resolution of the spectrum increases and the most intense vibronic band is the first one. We should note, in any case, that, although the lineshapes are very similar, the temperature broadening with the VH(C) and $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{2,eq})$ models have different explanations. With the VH(C) model, the effect can be traced back to the artifacts occurring in the ES frequency analysis at a non-stationary point using Cartesian coordinates, which induce additional coupling between GS and ES low frequency modes. For the $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{2,eq})$, specific effects arise from the non-orthogonality of the Duschinsky matrix that relates the normal modes defined at two different points, similarly to what is observed in the AH(I) model,²⁹ and eventually result in an overestimation of the Duschinsky couplings between low frequency modes of the GS and the intermediate frequency modes of the ES (see Figure S14 in SI). Consequently,

the similar lineshape provided by these three models, which are also in quite good agreement with the experimental ones, should be taken with care. Even though the $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{1,eq})$ does not suffer from any of the above issues, the remarkable differences observed with respect to the $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{2,eq})$ model, indicate that the changes of the \mathbf{G} matrix are too large to be confidently neglected. This rises a warning on the robustness of the predictions of the $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I})$ model, suggesting that, for \mathbf{VI} , more accurate results could only be obtained by accounting for the dependence of the \mathbf{G} matrix on the internal coordinates.

According to the above analysis, one might suspect that, for \mathbf{VI} , the good match between $\text{AH}(\mathbf{I})$, $\text{VH}(\mathbf{C})$ and $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{2,eq})$ simulated spectra and the experimental one at room temperature, might arise from a compensation of errors. For instance, the large temperature effect might be balanced by a smaller C=C progression that rules the main vibronic features. In order to test this hypothesis further, we have repeated the calculations modelling the GS and ES PESs with CAM-B3LYP, instead of PBE0 (B3LYP provides similar results to those at PBE0²⁹). In Figure 6, we present the simulations at 300 K with $\text{AH}(\mathbf{I})$, $\text{VH}(\mathbf{C})$ and both $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{1,eq})$ and $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{2,eq})$, comparing the results obtained with PBE0 and CAM-B3LYP. First of all, the relative performance of the different models using CAM-B3LYP is similar to that described for PBE0. Namely, $\text{AH}(\mathbf{I})$, $\text{VH}(\mathbf{C})$ and $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{2,eq})$ lead to spectra significantly broader and more structureless than $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{1,eq})$ predictions. Moreover, when CAM-B3LYP is used, the progression of the C=C stretching modes is larger with respect to the same progressions with PBE0. As a consequence, the spectra simulated with $\text{AH}(\mathbf{I})$, $\text{VH}(\mathbf{C})$ and $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{2,eq})$ models, which provide larger spectra, closely match the experimental lineshapes^{72,73} when PBE0 is used, while they are too broad with CAM-B3LYP. On the other hand, when the $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{1,eq})$ approach is used, the spectral width is underestimated with PBE0 but is significantly closer to the experiment for CAM-B3LYP. On the balance, however, the CAM-B3LYP progression seems to be larger than in the experiment, which may indicate some inaccuracies in the description of the ES, like a tendency to overestimate the change of bond orders from GS to ES.

The inconsistencies between the different models (mostly the large difference with the $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{1,eq})$ approach) indicate that even the apparently successful predictions achieved with PBE0 (or B3LYP) adopting $\text{AH}(\mathbf{I})$, $\text{VH}(\mathbf{C})$ and $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{2,eq})$ models should be taken with care. Such unreliability prevents us from assessing the best functional to treat the excited state of β -carotene. The discrepancies between PBE0 and CAM-B3LYP also indicate the limited accuracy of TDDFT for \mathbf{VI} . This finding is not completely unexpected, since, although we are dealing with its bright state characterized by a HOMO \rightarrow LUMO single-excitation, the difficulties related to the treatment of the low lying states of carotenoids are well known.^{74,75}

Figure 6: Lineshape spectra of molecule **VI** at 300 K simulated with AH model in internal coordinates and the VH one with either Cartesian or internal coordinates. The vibrational data are computed at either PBE0 (top) or CAM-B3LYP (centre). The experimental spectra registered in 3-methyl pentanone (3MP)⁷³ and chloroform⁷² are included for reference. The spectra are broadened by a Gaussian function with HWHM=0.01 eV.

5 Conclusion

In this work we investigated to what extent the adoption of curvilinear internal coordinates improve vertical models with respect to alternative protocols based on Cartesian (or linearised internal) coordinates, by performing an extensive analysis on a number of different systems.

We showed that adopting Cartesian coordinates (or equivalently coordinates obtained with a linear transformation of the \mathbf{x} set, like \mathbf{S} or \mathbf{Q}_1), the description of the shapes and frequencies of low-frequency modes, evaluated at non-stationary points, is problematic, leading even to the occurrence of spurious imaginary frequencies. These problems are solved using curvilinear internal coordinates.

Our new results indicate that vertical models in \mathbf{x} -frame are usually reliable for spectra at 0 Kelvin, while the problems with low-frequency modes can remarkably bias the prediction of thermal broadening at room temperature. Luckily, for most of the systems studied here, such differences, although noticeable, are not too large. On the balance the adoption of the \mathbf{s} -frame however allows to obtain

more accurate and robust results, and very importantly, permits to limit arbitrary choices like those made when neglecting the problematic modes or assigning them real frequencies.

Beside this main result, our analysis shows that the outcome of vertical models may strongly depend on the choice of the set of internal coordinates. Concretely, our results indicate that a redundant set of valence internal coordinates should be adopted, including all possible bonds, angles and dihedrals that arise from the connectivity pattern of the molecule. This conclusion is the same already reached by Baiardi et al. for adiabatic models.³⁴ Interestingly however, in vertical models the problems of using other internal coordinates, like those that define a Z-matrix, manifest in a different way. In adiabatic models, they do not affect frequencies and normal modes but essentially only the Duschinsky matrix (\mathbf{J}) and normal mode displacement vector (\mathbf{K}). At variance, we show that in vertical models the choice of the coordinate set may affect the normal modes and frequencies themselves (mainly the low-frequency ones), and that the usage of a redundant set allows to predict at the FC point frequencies and modes that are very similar to the “true” values computed at the minimum of the PES. On the contrary, the use of the non-redundant set arising from the Z-matrix may lead to large discrepancies. It is noteworthy that the better performance of redundant sets of internal coordinates we documented here is in line with the results of a number of seminal works in the field of the search for robust algorithms for the optimization of the molecular geometries.⁴¹⁻⁴⁴

In the protocol we worked out, the curvilinear nature of the internal coordinates is exactly considered in the transformation of the Hessian from Cartesian to internal coordinates. However, in order to keep the possibility itself to define a set of normal coordinates for the final state PES, exploiting, the simplicity of GF method, it is still necessary to simplify the kinetic operator in internal coordinates, assuming that the \mathbf{G} matrix remains unchanged upon the shift from the vertical point to the minimum. More specifically, in this work we highlight that two possibilities exist to build up a VH model, assigning to \mathbf{G} of the final state either the value $\mathbf{G}_{1,eq}$ or the value $\mathbf{G}_{2,eq}$. In keeping with the vertical hypothesis, we propose to use the value evaluated at the vertical point ($\mathbf{G}_{1,eq}$) since this also avoids non-orthogonality issues of the Duschinsky matrix that affect adiabatic models. Moreover, the choice $\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{G}_{1,eq}$ also makes not necessary the transformation of the structural shift in internal coordinates to Cartesian ones (required to compute $\mathbf{G}_{2,eq}$), which can be problematic.

Looking at these results from a different perspective, a further outcome of our analysis is to highlight that, in principle, even vertical models cannot be considered free from the problems connected with the dependence of \mathbf{G} on the internal coordinates, which manifest in adiabatic models with deviation from orthogonality of the Duschinsky matrix. In this context, we propose here a simple check of the validity of the approximation of considering $\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{G}_{1,eq}$ constant. This can be simply done *a posteriori* by evaluating the difference of the spectra computed

using $\mathbf{G}_{2,eq}$, i.e. the matrix evaluated at the minimum of the quadratic curve of the final state. Significant differences signal that the VH predictions cannot be considered fully robust and more accurate results would require to go beyond harmonic approximation and take into explicit account the dependence of \mathbf{G} on the nuclear coordinates.

For most of the molecules considered in this work, the simulations performed with the internal formulation adopting $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{1,eq})$ and $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{2,eq})$ models lead to very similar results. A very remarkable exception is observed for β -carotene, a molecule characterized by a large displacement along a torsion when going from the GS to the ES. In this case the spectra simulated with $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{1,eq})$ and $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{2,eq})$ provide quite different results. Namely, $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{2,eq})$ is noticeably affected by the same non-orthogonality issues that have already been reported with the adiabatic model,²⁹ and which result in larger Duschinsky couplings. Such effects are not present by definition in the $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{1,eq})$. Consequently, the spectra simulated with $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I}/\mathbf{G}_{2,eq})$ at room temperature are broader and, although this may reflect a “true” effect, we are sceptical that it could be adequately captured by the non-orthogonality of the Duschinsky matrix. This example allowed us to highlight that even $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I})$ protocol has limitations when the \mathbf{G} matrix changes significantly from the vertical point to the minimum of the quadratic PES of the final PES. When such difference is large, any simple harmonic approach reaches its limit of applicability and more refined methods should be adopted.⁵⁶

In conclusion, we showed that the protocol based on curvilinear internal coordinates improves the previous vertical models based on Cartesian coordinates and represents a robust and reliable vertical model to simulate the electronic line-shape. Therefore, with the limitations discussed above, $\text{VH}(\mathbf{I})$ model is expected to extend the range of applicability of standard harmonic methods adopted in recent literature and based on \mathbf{x} -, \mathbf{S} - or \mathbf{Q}_1 -frames toward the description of flexible molecules where the initial and final state minima are connected by sizeable structural displacements. In this context, it is important to highlight that the development of robust vertical models is an achievement of general interest well beyond the cases investigated in this contribution. There are in fact at least two general situations in which vertical models represent a more natural choice than adiabatic models. The first example is provided by quadratic vibronic coupling models (QVC) for nonadiabatic systems,⁷⁶ which are a straightforward generalization of the models discussed here to the cases when the electronic states are coupled (by linear or quadratic functions of the nuclear coordinates). The quest for a balanced description of the different electronic states naturally leads to the choice to expand at least their off-diagonal (coupling) PES around the ground-state geometry.⁷⁶ In fact any other (adiabatic) option would treat a state (the one in its minimum) differently from the others. Therefore all the issues investigated here for a single final PES are of direct relevance also for QVC models, and the adoption of \mathbf{s} -frame will provide the right framework to investigate their impact. The second example is provided by complex scenarios like very flexible systems, or

even semirigid systems embedded in heterogeneous environments that deserve an atomistic (explicit) description, which surely represent an hot topic in current research.^{23,77–79} In particular when the system, or the system+environment becomes large, it is clear that the number of modes increase steeply and many low-frequency modes appear. In this kind of systems, it is likely that the vibronic resolution is lost and low-frequency modes follow a classical statistical behaviour. However, the adoption of a fully classical approach to compute the spectrum may not be satisfactory, since quantum effects on high-frequency modes can still dominate the width of the spectra (see e.g. ref. 80). Recent attempts^{37,81} have been proposed to describe these systems with hybrid quantum/classical (QC) approaches, assuming that they are dynamically separated in sub-systems, a fast one comprising short-amplitude high-frequency modes and a slow one comprising large-amplitude modes, like torsions, coupled to the environment. More advanced modelling of these systems will benefit from the ability to define fast-modes Hamiltonians at geometries that are out of equilibrium for the slow modes, therefore following a “vertical philosophy”. The full understanding of the potentiality and limitations of the **s**-frame vertical model here investigated is a necessary step for these further developments.

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Supporting Information

Derivation of the normal mode analysis in the **x**- and **Q**₁-frames; analysis of the rotational and vibrational modes with different models for molecules **I** and **VI**; representation of the projections from A to V(I) and V(C) modes for molecules **I** to **VI**; Duschinsky matrices evaluated with AH, VH(I) and VH(C) for molecules **I** to **VI**; discussion on the symmetry of the Hessian in internal coordinates; discussion on the spectral shift between AH, VH(C) and VH(I) models; analysis of the frequencies computed with A, V(C) and V(I) models for molecules **I** to **VI**; checks on the choice of real frequencies for imaginary modes for molecule **II** and comparison of the simulated spectra for molecules **I-V** with experimental data; analysis of the deviations in the shifts in redundant coordinates upon the transformation to Cartesian coordinates for molecules **I** to **VI**; simulation of the spectra with (I/**G**_{1,eq}) and (I/**G**_{2,eq}) models for molecules **I** to **VI**. This information is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>

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